

Managing Default in Musharakah Mutanaqisah

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M*usharakah mutanaqisah*, or diminishing partnership, is a relatively new technique that is not found in classical literature. It has been formulated by contemporary Muslim scholars to facilitate investments among Muslims. Although the mechanism of musharakah mutanaqisah (MM) was approved by the First International Conference on Islamic Banking, held in Dubai in 1979, it has not been widely implemented in the Islamic financial industry. Currently, MM is implemented in Malaysia and UK, where the necessary amendments to the prevailing laws have been made. Banks in Middle East make relatively less use of MM and its variants.

Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM), in its Financial Stability and Payment Systems Report 2007, defined MM as “a form of partnership in which one partner promises to gradually acquire the equity share of the other partner until the share of ownership is completely transferred to the first partner.”

The Mechanism of MM

The MM model can be easily implemented for various financing purposes. However, it is most commonly used for home financing. Basic steps involved in the MM structure for home financing are illustrated in *Figure 1* below.

1. Customer selects house and applies for the financing
2. Bank, once application is approved, enters into a Musharakah arrangement with customer
3. Customer leases Bank's share in the house
4. Customer makes an additional monthly payment, along with the rent, to buy the Bank's stake in the property.
5. The partnership will be terminated with the customer owning 100% of the house; the title will be transferred to him/ her.

As can be seen above, MM creates a complex set of relationships, rights and obligations between the partners. Thus the risk profiles would be different from some other financing arrangements. According to the BNM report, financial institutions are exposed to both market risk and credit risk. The former is associated with the joint ownership of the underlying property, while the latter is related to the ability of the customer to buy and of the financial institution to sell its share. Therefore, for successful implementation by financial institutions, this mechanism requires prudent and efficient risk management based on reliable and adequate data.

Practical Example of MM Default

In the event of default, the termination of MM can be done in two ways as briefly stated by BNM Financial Stability and Payment Systems Report 2007: (i) without *wa'ad* (purchase undertaking); & (ii) with *wa'ad*. In the first case, the underlying asset will be sold in the market and the proceeds will be shared between the partners according to the latest ownership share ratio (after all the outstanding costs and payments, such as outstanding rents and legal fees, are covered).

In the second case, the customer is required to buy the remaining shares of the bank. *Wa'ad* in default creates a legal obligation on the customer to buy all outstanding shares of the bank and to pay outstanding rental and other fees. Through this process, a debt is created, and this debt is to be paid by the customer.

Table 1: Musharakah Mutanaqisah in the Event of Default.

Issue	Without Wa'ad		With Wa'ad	
	1	2	3	
Cost of the House		RM100,000		RM100,000
Customer's Share (C)		RM10,000		RM10,000
Bank's Share (B)		RM90,000		RM90,000
Equity Ratio C:B		10:90		10:90
Default after 3 yrs				
Customer's Share		RM30,000		RM30,000
Bank's Share		RM70,000		RM70,000
Equity Ration C:B		30:70		30:70
Creates Indebtedness		No		Yes
Sales proceeds	C-Share	B-Share	C-Share	B-Share
Price RM90,000	RM27,000	RM63,000	RM20,000*	RM70,000*
Price RM70,000	RM21,000	RM49,000	RM0**	RM70,000**
Price RM60,000	RM18,000	RM42,000	-RM10,000***	RM70,000***

Source: Author's own

Note: For simplicity of discussion, we will ignore the outstanding rental and legal fees.

*The bank will claim all of the outstanding amount owned by the customer, while any surplus will be given to the customer.

** Banks use wa'ad to create indebtedness, and the full amount is to be paid by the customer to a bank. Thus, if the proceeds are equal to the amount claimed, the customer will not receive anything, as his/her equity shares will be used to pay off the outstanding amount.

*** On the other hand, if the proceeds are less than the amount claimed, the bank will go after the customer for the remaining balance.

From Table 1 above, we can see the difference in case of default when MM is implemented without wa'ad and with wa'ad. In short, when MM is implemented without wa'ad, the property will be sold in the market. If there is a surplus, it will be shared between the parties based on the profit-sharing ratio. On the other hand, if there is a loss, it will be shared according to the capital share of each party.

However, in most cases banks use wa'ad (purchase undertaking). It obliges the customer to buy all of the bank's outstanding share (in our case, RM70,000). However, as the customer will generally not be able to do so, MM will be terminated and the underlying property will be sold at auction. The selling price of the house could be higher, lower, or equal to the amount claimed.

If the house is sold for, say, RM90,000, then RM70,000 will be paid to the bank for its share in the house. The additional RM20,000 will be entirely given to the customer. However, if the selling price is equal to the outstanding amount, the customer will receive nothing, as the proceeds will be entirely used to cover the amount claimed by the bank. Finally,

if the proceeds are less than the amount claimed, the bank will go after the customer for the remaining balance (i.e. RM10,000). One thing is for sure, in case default in MM is managed through wa'ad, the bank is guaranteed its outstanding amount. Regardless of the selling price, the bank will receive the amount claimed, RM70,000.

It is worth noting that in the above cases the proceeds will first be used to cover all costs related to the legal action and property disposal. Overdue rental payments and the bank's outstanding share would be settled next. Finally, in case of PU as practiced by KFH, the remaining balance (if any) will be completely given to the customer. On the other hand, if PU is not used, any remaining balance will be shared between the bank and the customer according to their current ownership ratio.

Issue of Default In MM as Implemented in Malaysia

Based on the discussion above, it can be concluded that MM, as implemented in Malaysia with regard to the management of default cases, is the same as al-bay' bithaman ajil (BBA).

"Currently, MM, by the local standards, is not much different from BBA. Most financial institutions promote only equity financing for diminishing of the equity, but basically most of the process is similar to BBA...especially when it comes to default cases; banks will still go through the same channel to dispose the property, which is via auction, using wa'ad," says an industry observer.

"When it comes to an event of default," says Maybank Islamic's head of product management Zariah Abu Samah, "similar procedures or processes and legal proceedings practiced under the current home financing, including BBA, are applicable."

She further elaborated that the difference between BBA and MM lies in the up-front transactions, i.e. BBA is based on a sale and purchase of property, while MM would require both a customer and a financier/bank to jointly purchase the property, with the customer's undertaking to gradually acquire the bank's share of ownership in the property, ending in the former owning the property.

One of the reasons for this approach lies in the fact that banks take a charge

over the property. Asian Finance Bank's chief credit officer, Ismail Aminuddin, shared his experience, commenting, "Because banks take a charge over the land [property], instead of using trust agreement in case of default, they have to follow the National Land Code. We should not take a charge; we should use trust agreement. However, there are some issues relating to trust agreement that need to be sorted out with the government."

Kuwait Finance House (KFH) Malaysia is the only bank that does not take a charge, according to a senior legal source at KFH. Currently, in the event of default, KFH has two options:

1. **Wa'ad (Purchase Undertaking-PU):** Here, the bank will invoke the customer's purchase undertaking and exercise its right of wa'ad that was given by the customer. If a customer fails to pay the claimed amount, the bank will use its right as trustee to sell the property. (The outcome is explained in Table 1 above).
2. **Without wa'ad:** The bank, as trustee, sells the property. "The proceeds will first be used to pay the parties' capital. Any surplus will be shared between the parties based on profit-share ratio. If there is a loss, the loss will be shared according to the capital. This is, perhaps, a truer version of MM," a KFH legal source says. "This option is specified in the agreement without referring to the PU."

Although KFH has these options available in the event of default, the first option is the most likely to be followed, and "it is the one that mirrors typical home financing the most," says the legal source.

Another reason why banks prefer using wa'ad in case of defaults is the current practice and the way the financial system operates. Although there are no legal impediments to implement a true MM in Malaysia according to the KFH legal source and Zariah of Maybank Islamic implementing a true MM would affect the way regulatory bodies treat it and how banks would account for it, and it would have an impact on capital charge. In other words, "the risk weight would increase to about 200-300 per cent. What we apply currently is only 50 per cent," says Zariah of Maybank Islamic.

"It is due to the prevailing conventional banking system and its mechanism that the true MM is not a viable option. It is possible to have true MM under the current system, but it would be much more expensive. The bank would charge you, let say 8 per cent instead of market value 5 per cent to account for additional risk that it is taking," Fajr Capital's Managing Director Rafe Haneef says.

On this matter, an industry observer begs to differ. In her view, "The Malaysian Government is always open for discussion and very supportive of the Islamic banking industry. Any challenges in terms of laws and everything related to the product are open for discussion and review by the respective party, such as BNM and AIBIM, as well as the Land Office. The only thing that we need is willingness from the industry and which MM concept they want to use."

Conclusion

Most banks say that they do not want to use MM because there are many issues and because it has not been tested in court. Although there has

been no legal case to test the MM mechanism, the question is: Are we going to wait another 10-15 years to implement this model? Are we going to implement MM properly, or we will make only cosmetic changes and after 10-15 years realize that there is something wrong?

"I believe it goes back to the willingness of the financial institutions. If we want to create changes for the industry and to take Malaysia Islamic industry to another level, we must be ready to take the challenge. If we look back to 20-30 years ago when the industry wanted to implement BBA, there were lots of hassles in terms of laws and everything related to the product, including educating the customer, the developer and whoever, but we did it. Agreed, there are many issues to be handled in order to implement MM properly, but this is what we call a learning curve. It goes back to the willingness to take risk and to make it different from the existing BBA as well as conventional," an industry observer concludes.

The above discussion is a mere theoretical approach to shed some lights on the issue of default. Nevertheless, it is been noted that there is a tendency among banks to use wa'ad (purchase undertaking). Using wa'ad defeats the spirit of MM and the underlying principle of profit-and-loss sharing, as it creates debt by which the interests of banks are protected at the expense of customers. "For me, if we do MM properly, if we handle the laws and everything related to this product, then this product can kill conventional products," Ismail of Asian Finance Bank believes.